

OLIVE TREE'S PRUNING HARVESTING USING THE GREEK MODIFIED MULCHER FOTOPOULOS FSR2000, MACHINE PERFORMANCES AND BIOMASS QUALITY EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT: Pruning's residues could be an important source for renewable energy production. However their use for this aim is actually hindered by various fences mainly linked to the lacking in harvesting phases and to the absence of a sustainable logistic chain for energy production. Considering this the AGROinLOG (Demonstration of innovative integrated biomass logistics centres (IBLC) for the Agro-industry sector in Europe) project aimed to develop Innovative Biomass Logistic Centres enhancing agricultural residues within existing production cycles. One of the study area of the project was Agios Kostantinos (Greece), a Greek locality in which the most important crop is olive tree. In this context pruning residues are actually seen mostly as a problem and not as a potential resource. According to what written above AGROinLOG activities in this study area aimed to develop a sustainable harvesting system for pruning residues, evaluating the performances of different machines currently available on market with a particular focus on machine performances and obtained biomass quality, in order to identify the best possible alternative for olive trees' pruning harvesting and comminuting. One of the tested machine was the Greek Fotopoulos FSR2000. Conducted tests allowed to obtain an overall evaluation of this machine with particular references to work productivity, obtained biomass quality and economic performance of the harvesting systems. Notwithstanding Fotopoulos FSR2000 showed good performances for what concerning productivity and costs, obtained biomass quality resulted poor. Moreover the machine shows substantial design limits, for example the lack of a properly pick-up system. Thus Fotopoulos FSR2000 could represent an idea in order to minimize the initial investment but other machines, currently available on market, seemed to be more suitable for the aim of developing a IBLC in Agios Kostantinos context.

Keywords: biomass, harvesting, wood chip

1 INTRODUCTION

AGROinLOG (Demonstration of innovative integrated biomass logistics centres for the Agro-industry sector in Europe) project' main goal is the demonstration of Integrated Biomass Logistics Centres (IBLC) for food and non-food products, evaluating their technical, environmental and economic feasibility. The project is based on three agro-industries in the fodder (Spain), olive oil production (Greece) and cereal processing (Sweden) sectors that are willing to deploy new business lines in their facilities to open new markets in bio-commodities (energy, transport and manufacturing purposes) and intermediate bio-products (transport and biochemical). These sectors represent over 10% turnover of agro-industries and 30% of those with inherent synergies to integrate food and non-food business taking advantage of their existing equipment, seasonality and established food logistic. Main challenges of the project are based on being able to integrate logistics, harvesting and equipment in food and non-food applications, ensuring marketability of the final bio-commodities.

Harvesting is a key stage that influences the product quality [1,2], the type of logistics chain and the economic sustainability of the pruning supply chain [3,4]. For this reason many machine manufacturers have developed dedicated implements for collecting pruning residues [5–

10]. According to what written above the selection of an appropriate harvesting systems, and so an accurate evaluation of different suitable machines, is a fundamental step to the demonstration of an IBLC.

Thus the aim of the present study was machine performances and biomass quality evaluation in olive trees' pruning harvesting conducted with Fotopoulos FSR2000. This machine is a modified mulcher for pruning residues collection. Conducted analysis consisted in evaluating: machine working behavior (field capacity, material capacity, production percentage losses, fuel consumption), obtained biomass quality (bulk density and particle size distribution) and costs analysis. Moreover a qualitative evaluation of the machine was conducted in order to find values and defects of it, allowing to fully checking the possibility of using Fotopoulos FSR2000 as harvesting system for pruning's residues in Agios Kostantinos context.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Machine description

The Fotopoulos machine consists in a modified mulcher for pruning residues collection. The main modifications to the original machine are the carter removal and the installation of an unloading system

constituted by a rectangular drain which collects the mulched material and moved it thanks to an air flux for 2 m distance discharging it on a big bag mounted on 4 hooks. The discharge height corresponds to 1.5 m. This machine is not equipped with a properly pick-up system. Harvester's width is 2 m, so in order to collect the overall pruning's material It needed 2 passes.

About big bag's discharging system it consists in an hydraulic pump powered by the tractor which can open and close the neck and lift down the big bag directly on field. Subsequently the big bag has to be taken by the tractor's fork lift and moved outside the field.

2.2 Pre-harvest field characterization

Homogeneous area of at least 9 rows were selected to perform the test. The experimental field was divided in 3 blocks of similar surface (at least three rows per block). If the olive grove does not have a well defined planting pattern, the total surface has been divided in three blocks of similar surface. Information collected were: age of the olive grove, field slope (%), presence of stones, average pruning diameter, average pruning length, distance between the rows, distance between trees within the rows. Moreover machine characteristics were recorded, in particular: machine weights, needed power of the tractor, volume capacity of the collection system, original price, service life (years), machine usages (hours/years).

2.3 Harvesting tests

2.3.1 Machine performances

In each experimental unit, the performance of the machines will be evaluated through the study of the working times according to the standards ASAE S495 DEC99. In particular investigated parameters were:

- **Field Speed (km/h):** is the average rate of machine travel in the field during an uninterrupted period of functional activity. Average field speed can be easily measured by marking off a fixed distance (at least 100 m) in the field, placing a mark at each end, and counting the seconds it takes to drive between the marks.
- **Theoretical Field Capacity (ha/h):** depends only on the full operating width of the machine and the average travel speed in the field. It represents the maximum possible field capacity that can be obtained at the given field speed when the full operating width of the machine is being used. It is calculated multiplying the field speed for the working width of the machine.
- **Effective Field Capacity (ha/h):** The Effective Field Capacity of a farm machine is the rate at which it performs its primary function, i.e., the number of hectares that can be harvested per hour.
- **Measurements or estimates of machine capacities** are used to schedule field operations, power units, labor, and to estimate machine operating costs. The effective field capacity (EFC) of a machine in the field can be easily calculated by dividing the hectares completed by the hours of Operative Time (OT). The operative time is the real time necessary to complete the harvest of the surface object of the test, including also turnings, stops, regulations, etc.
- **Material Capacity (t/h):** The working capacity of harvesting machines can be measured also by the quantity of material harvested per hour. This capacity is called the machine's material capacity (MC), expressed as tons per hour (t/h). It is the product of the machine's EFC

and the average yield of crop per hectare

- **Fuel Consumption:** Fuel consumption can be determined through machine tank refilling until full level at the end of each experimental unit (plot) using a graduated large cylinders to define the volume of fuel consumed (l/ha or l/t of biomass harvested). Another way could be to weight the amount of fuel consumed (kg of diesel/ha or kg/t of biomass harvested). It is important to start each experimental unit with the tank completely full. The fuel consumed must be proportioned to the exact surface of the experimental unit tested in order to define the fuel consumed per hectare in that experimental unit.

2.3.2 Post harvest measurements

Other important parameters were evaluated after the end of harvesting operation. In particular:

- **Yield of biomass (t_{fm}/ha):** After the harvesting, the biomass collected in each block will be weighed using a dynamometer connected to a tractor with fork.
- **Biomass losses (%):** To determine the losses of pruning, three transects per plot (large like the width of the harvester per 5 m long) will be randomly identified along the rows and all the biomass left on the ground inside the transects will be collected by hand and weighed on field by a dynamometer. Therefore, the area of each transect will be equal to 5 m (long side) per the pick-up system width of the harvester, in order to determine pruning losses to be proportioned to the surface of one hectare.
- **Bulk density (EN 15103:2009; kg/m^3):** Bulk density is an important parameter for fuel deliveries on volume basis and together with the net calorific value, it determines the energy density. It also facilitates the estimation of space requirements for transport and storage. The test portion is filled into a standard container of a given size and shape and is weighed afterwards. Bulk density is calculated from the net weight per standard volume and given for the measured moisture content. The container shall be cylindrically shaped and manufactured of a shock resistant, smooth-surfaced material. The container shall be resistant to deformation in order to prevent any variation in shape and volume. The container has to be waterproof. For easier handling grips may be fixed externally. The height-diameter-ratio shall be within 1,25 and 1,50. The large measuring container has a filling volume of 50 l (0,05 m^3) volume. The volume may deviate by 1 l (= 2 %). It shall have an effective (inner) diameter of 360 mm and an effective (inner) height of 491 mm. Deviations from these dimensions are tolerable, if the height-diameter-ratio remains within 1,25 and 1,50.
- **Moisture content (EN 14774-2:2009 (E); %):** Before the harvesting test, 5 samples of pruning 1 kg each will be taken to determine the moisture content of the pruning and, consequently the dry matter in the pruning. Samples for the determination of total moisture content shall be sampled and shall be received in the laboratory in sealed air-tight containers or packings. Weigh an empty clean drying container to the nearest 0,1 g, transfer the sample from the container or bag to the drying container. In case of moisture left on the inner surfaces of the bag or container, this amount of moisture shall be included in the calculation of the moisture content. Weigh the drying container with the sample and place it in the oven controlled at $(105 \pm 2) ^\circ C$. Heat the container with the sample until constant in mass.

Constancy in mass is defined as a change not exceeding 0,2 % of the total loss in mass during a further period of heating at $(105 \pm 2) ^\circ\text{C}$ over a period of 60 min. The drying time required will depend on the particle size of the sample, the rate of atmosphere change in oven, the thickness of the sample layer, etc. Dried solid biofuels are hygroscopic and the drying container with the sample shall be re-weighed to the nearest 0,1 g when still hot within 10 s to 15 s to avoid absorption of moisture. The total moisture content shall be calculated using Equation (1) and the result shall be given on a wet basis.

$$\text{Mar} = \frac{(M_2 - M_3) + M_4}{(M_2 - M_1) + M_4} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where

Mar is the moisture content in the biofuel, as received, expressed as a percentage by mass;

M₁ is the mass in g of the empty drying container;

M₂ is the mass in g of the drying container and sample before drying;

M₃ is the mass in g of the drying container and sample after drying;

M₄ is the mass in g of the moisture associated with the packing.

The result shall be calculated to two decimal places and rounded to the nearest 0,1 % for reporting.

- Particle size distribution (CEN/TS 15149-1:2006 (E): the determination of the size distribution of particulate biofuels was done by the oscillating screen method. The minimum size of the test sample for the determination of the size distribution shall be 8 l. For fine grade biofuels, where 100 % of the particles pass the sieve holes of 45 mm diameter, a smaller sample size of minimum 4 l can be used.

2.4 Cost analysis

Economic evaluation of the harvesting systems was conducted using ABC (Activity Basic Costing) standard. Costs were reported in €/h, €/ha and €/t. Moreover an evaluation of the economic performance of the harvesting system was done considering a wood chips price of 38.41 €/t ([11]).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Machine Performances

About Theoretical Field capacity Fotopoulos machine showed a 0.39 ha/h value which decreases to 0.28 ha/h considering effective Field Capacity. Material capacity reached 1.31 t/h considering a yield of 4.75 t_{fm}/ha. Production losses were 21%.

About fuel consumption this machine showed a value of 2.7 l/t_{fm} and of 6.85 l/ha.

For what concerning harvested biomass quality bulk density analysis showed a value of 205 kg/m³. An overall view of the machine performances is given in Table I. Particle size distribution of the obtained biomass is reported in Figure 1.

Table I: Machine performances of Fotopoulos FSR2000

Variable	Value
Theoretical Field Capacity [ha/h]	0.39
Effective Field Capacity [ha/h]	0.28
Material Capacity [t/h]	1.31
Yield [t _{fm} /ha]	4.75
Production Losses [%]	21
Fuel Consumption [l/t _{fm}]	2.7
Fuel Consumption [l/ha]	6.85
Biomass Bulk Density [kg/m ³]	205

Figure 1: particle size distribution

3.2 Cost analysis

About cost analysis Fotopoulos FSR2000 yard, composed by a 55 kw (75 hp) tractor and Fotopoulos FSR2000 modified mulcher; showed a cost of 23.63 €/h, 84.80 €/ha and 17.77 €/t. The amount of the initial investment is 47341.00 €. Considering an estimated price of wood chips equal to 38.41 €/t, economic performance of the yard corresponds to a surplus of 20.64 €/t. It is important to underline which the costs of preliminary raking operation were not considered because generally this is not competence of the IBLC but of the single farmer.

Summarize of cost analysis of Fotopoulos FSR2000 harvesting system is given in **Table II** Table .

Table II: results of cost analysis of Fotopoulos FSR2000

	Unit	Hog fuel
Market price	€/t	38.41
Yield	t/ha	4.75
Fotopoulos FSR2000	€/h	2.43
	€/ha	8.69
	€/t	1.83
55 kw tractor	€/h	21.20
	€/ha	75.71
	€/t	15.94
Total cost of the harvesting system (excluding preliminary raking operation)	€/h	23.63
	€/ha	84.80
	€/t	17.77
Economic performance	€/t	20.64

3.3 Qualitative evaluation of the machine

Fotopoulos FSR2000 showed essentially four substantial limits. The first one concerns the absence of a pick-up system which causes soil collection together with biomass when the soil is not levelled. The second one is related to the big bag's ground clearance, which is not sufficient to avoid the train of the big bag on soil which can cause damage to this and consequently biomass leakage. Moreover the loading systems based on big bags implies a further operation consisting in collecting big bags with a tractor, thus negatively influencing work productivity and so costs. Finally the 2 m width makes impossible to collect overall biomass in one single passage and so 2 passages were needed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Summarizing, Fotopoulos FSR2000 presented a lower work productivity and a lower biomass quality in comparison with other machines analyzed within AGROinLOG project. Moreover it showed a consistent biomass loss.

According to what written above Fotopoulos FSR2000 could represent an idea in order to minimize the initial investment but other machines, currently available on market, seemed to be more suitable for the aim of developing a IBLC in Agios Kostantinos context. However conducted tests made possible to identify the weakness which could be in olive trees' pruning harvesting and to detect the possible enhancements in order to ensure good machine performances and suitable biomass quality.

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